

ISSN 2519-9781

***A Study Analysis on Challenges and Opportunities
for Somali education system (2016-2021)***

Dr. Abdishakur Sh Hassan Faqih

Associate professor, Faculty of Education, Mogadishu University

Email: faqih99@gmail.com

Abstract

The Somali education system came through a difficult transition from total destruction into recovery scheme. While progress was achieved over the last years in the provision of the development of public education, the frequency ensuing period of insecurity led to a disruption of normal socio-economic life in many areas of the country. Consequently, the country has incorporated matters of education quality reform and policy-making processes. It is therefore clear that education sector in the country is facing different challenges, opportunities and trends requiring reforms in the management and governance styles. The rise of partners, internal factors, together with the rapid pace is created and utilized. There is an urgent need for institutions of quality performs to adjust rapidly the needs of the education system, and to deal with some of these trends, challenges and developments.

The study objectives are outlining the lines of change affecting education systems in the last four years (2016-2020) to review the challenges and opportunity in the performance and its progress including the capacity and gaps. Actual fieldwork was carried out in federal and federal state institution capacity in general with the understanding that there are significant differences across the different regions of Somalia.

The findings are challenges of high rates of school abrasion and poor learning outcomes, as well as weak capacities, limited available resource, which effective services deliver, there is a growing need for regulation in all education sectors and coordination challenges in decentralized education sector provision. The needs come into key factors across the subsectors that could affect learning and enrolment in the schools.

Keywords: Quality Assurance, Challenges, Opportunities, Policy and MECHE

1. Introduction

As the foundation and essential driving force of economic, social, and human development, education is at the heart of the change that is dramatically affecting our world in the areas of science, technology, economics, and culture. It is the reason behind social change and scientific progress, and in its turn, it is subjected to the results of progress that it itself has engendered, both with regard to content as well as methods and established aims. (Sadegh Bakhtiari, 2011).

The right to education for every Somali citizen is enshrined in the constitution under Article 30, which also underscores the right to free

education for every child up to secondary level (Draft constitution 2012). Somalia education having suffered major and prolonged disruption continues to require special attention in the process of national reconstruction and development.

Global obligations assure vital exchange experience enhancing many areas of the human development especially education; it's a major concern for all societies. Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) obliged all governments to have in place strategies that ensure achievement to advance sustainable socio-economic development; those goals' timeframe was in 2000-2015. The international civil society network (Social Watch) pointed out in 2013, that Somalia is unlikely to meet most, if any, of the (MDGs). (Social Watch 2013) Eventually, the country failed to improve one indicator of the (MDGs) including education sector development. In September 2015 United Nations member countries committed global Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) for target deadline is 2030. Goal 4 ensures inclusive and equitable quality education and promotes lifelong learning opportunities for all. (UN, 2015) The main barriers to education in Somalia include, limited oversight and outreach by Ministry of education, insufficient resource, it has limited control over education services this means that there are a wide variety of actors offering education which is outside of the control of the government. The policy gap limits ministry's ability to monitor and enforce quality education as stipulated in the constitution and the National Development Plan. To address the education sector challenges, the ministry requires to reform and set clear policies, standards and guidelines. However, the study provides the findings based

on the situational analysis, strategic plans of the ministry and needs established to align the education sector with the National development agenda of the Federal Government of Somalia.

2. Statement of the problem

How the system can overcome the challenges and maintain opportunities? While there are prospects for the Somali education system moving forward, it is yet to be achieved the desired outcome. The system delivery and its capacities in federal and state level have remained weak with very limited resources to support service delivery. The real challenge is inadequate finance, low capacity of the human resource, in addition to inconsistent ministerial policy, lack of minimal standards, poor coordination and poor decision-making infrastructure.

3. Objectives of the study

The study seeks to achieve the following objectives:

1. To review the challenges and opportunity in the Somali education system performance and it's progress including the capacity and gaps.
2. To provides the findings of the capacity analysis and makes recommendation based on the situational analysis especially the internal and external capacity of the system.
3. To review the education system structures, management and responsibilities, focusing on the analyzing systems, processes and mechanisms for performing the functions to determine the efficiency.

4. Determine the managerial and governing skills gaps as well as suitability for tasks undertaken to determine quality needs.

4. Research questions

1. Is the education system in Somalia having enough capacity to deliver a relevant quality education for Somali people?
2. What is the current challenge and opportunity requiring to harmonizing policies, maintain resources, capacity building, curriculum development, teacher training and sustain quality education?

5. Significance of the study

The study contributes to understanding in depth how the functional role of the education system in Somalia is suitable in the last four years; this will help to safeguard institutional mission and identity.

Methodology

Methodology consists mainly of literature and documentary study reviews method used to collect, analyze and interpret available data and publications to find patterns and generalized results to research questions. The assessment and data analysis is carried out through contents and discourse analysis included:

1. Reviewing on the existing documents in the Ministry of Education Culture and Higher Education for the last four years to assess real performance of education systems, processes and

mechanisms through determining the challenges and opportunities of education subsectors developments.

2. The review focused on the annual joint reviews documents. Education Sector Strategic Plan (ESSP) related documents. The school mapping and needs assessment documents, national curriculum framework and teacher training documents.
3. The study also used analyzing interviews with a sample of some ministry members and education experts, interviewed to determine challenges and opportunities.

Education System Situation Analysis:

Under the capacity development, the ministry of education is working towards reversing factors that undermine delivery of quality education in the Federal Government of Somalia including limited education sector capacities, infrastructure and basic facilities. The Ministry works with other key stakeholders in the sector including the government, private sector, civil society organizations and development partners. The private education remains the major players in the education sector to date, governing 60% of schools. There is wide variation in levels of development between urban, rural and nomadic areas, between males and females, and between different regions of Somalia. (MECHE, JRES, 2019).

The education sector in Somalia comprises of six sub sectors: (The National Development Plan 2017-2019)

- 1- Pre-Primary education

- 2- Primary Education
- 3- Secondary Education
- 4- Technical vocational Education and Training (TVET)
- 5- Higher education
- 6- Non-Formal Education

There is no uniform education system as the education sector is largely managed and supported by partners, including regional administrations, international NGOs, Community Education Committees (CECs), community-based organizations (CBOs), education umbrella groups and networks, NGOs, private sector, and religious groups. There is wide variation about the levels of education services delivered by the government between the different regions. Various state authorities have developed their own policies and strategies to fit into their unique contexts and leverage their diverse potentials. (MECHE, JRES, 2019)

The government is responsible for providing quality public education in the country. Ministry of Education in federal and state level mandate is to deliver a relevant and quality education and training for all Somalia. They have limited control over education services in many areas, and have no harmonized curriculum, teacher training and limited supported teaching force. This means that there are a wide variety of factors such as civil society and private institutions offering education, which is sometimes outside of the jurisdiction and control of the government. (MECHE, JRES, 2019).

The major barriers to education in Somalia include lack of security, insufficient teachers, limited oversight and outreach. (National Development Plan 2017-2019). Somalia has one of the world's lowest gross enrolment rates for primary school-aged children in sub-Saharan Africa at 30 percent children at primary education level and 26 percent for secondary education. (The Somalia education cluster report, 2017). Over-age enrollment is very common all throughout the Somali formal school system due to delayed entry at the primary level which affects the entry at secondary and tertiary levels of education. (National Development Plan 2017-2019).

The National Development Plan acknowledges “the high number of over aged children enrolled in school (35% are aged 14-17 years, and 15% are 18 years or older) with the country's enrollment to secondary being the lowest in the region”. The policy gap in the education sector has continued to deny the children of Somalia equitable access to quality education as stipulated in the constitution and the National Development Plan as it limits ministry of education ability to monitor and enforce quality education best practices in the country. Otherwise, the education system has been hampered by lack of credible data, which had an effect on planning. Data is primarily collected via partner NGOs and INGOs although all partners were not willing to share data with the government with limited oversight on their provenance and limited capacity to deliver interventions due to security, logistics, and financial challenges. (The National Development Plan 2017-2019) According to the finance directorate of federal ministry of education that ‘total 5.01% of the national budget (2%), has been allocated to education. (1.5%)

contributing to budget allocation for Somali National University. (0.5%) Somali Academy of Science & Arts. The clear increase in domestic financing demonstrates the government's commitment to the education sector. Further increases to 12% are required to achieve the 2020 target. (MECHE, JRES, 2019). The lack of funds in the sector has affected the operational and maintenance costs for schools and the recruitment of qualified and provision of adequate and appropriate teaching and learning materials including textbooks. (National Development Plan 2017-2019)

There are no systematic teacher training and continuous professional development programmes, many teachers in schools are without professional pedagogical and teaching skills. The existing in-service training requires a standardized term and frequency to ensure teachers acquire necessary skills. Some of education workers such as umbrella groups are currently filling the gap vacated by the government in training teachers. (MECHE, 2019)

Some other challenge embedded in teaching language. The adoption of a language as a medium of teaching is a policy decision that should be based on research evidence and with an eye to the future, including the implication of language on identity and local culture. There is multiple medium of instruction. Arabic, Somali and English are now used in the schools. Public schools use Somali language, as an instruction language while privately owned schools use English and Arabic. The draft education policy favors use of English as a language of instruction in schools. (MECHE, 2019).

The federal ministry of education faced several challenges, including: Insufficient of standardized Curriculum. The education system in the country is not coordinated posing curriculum management challenges. There are parallel systems based on the curriculum. Most schools used 4-4-4 systems in which students spend four years each at primary, intermediate and secondary schools while other schools used the 6-3-3 systems where students spend six years in primary, three in intermediate and three in secondary. (MECHE, 2019)

Educational policies reform is an important issue in any post conflict nation. Somali education systems policies require an intensive effort from all the nationwide to establish a suitable policy emphasis on quality education and promote international education standards to enhance competitiveness of Somali citizens to compete for opportunities globally. The federal government of Somalia has made some strides in the development of the education systems and structure but still lacks key policies. Political and social risks affecting communities in Somalia have led to displacement, delays and upset. There are some education policies and strategies in draft form and awaiting approval including;

Education Sector Strategic Plan (ESSP) 2018-2020. The plan aimed to overcome the challenges contributing to limited access to quality education, inequity, weak governance, poor service delivery and limited sector capacity. The strategy is based on international goals and conventions such as Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) and Education for All (EFA), the Convention of the Rights of the Child (CRC), the International Safe Schools Declaration, and national

development agenda spelt out in the Constitution, the Education Act and the National Development Plan 2017-2019. The strategy is the sector-guiding document for planning, partnerships and implementation of programs. (MECHE, 2019)

Draft Education Policy 2017. Ministry of Education drafted the education policy create an enabling environment for quality education and sector development. (MECHE, 2019)

National Curriculum Framework 2017. Ministry of Education developed a curriculum framework with the support of UNICEF. (MECHE, 2017)

Challenges and Opportunities for education Access and quality

The quality of education is ultimately judged by learning outcomes of children in school and literacy rates. The overall adult literacy rate, which according to the 1975 population census was 54 percent, dropped to 40 percent. According to Population Estimate Survey for Somalia (PESS ,2014), main reasons for this decline were civil war and conflict. However, now literacy rates are higher for younger Somalis, which demonstrate that there have been improvements in educational quality generally. Since 2011, roughly are 2.6 million children and adolescents have enrolled in primary education across Somalia. While this is impressive progress in enrolment, the national Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) for primary education has remained low at 30 per cent for primary level and 26.5 per cent at secondary level. The Net Enrolment Ratio (NER) for both primary and secondary levels is considerably lower than

the comparable Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) at both levels. (UNICEF 2017)

In 2019, a total of 1,159 schools were mapped in Benadir and some federal member states (FMS) except Puntland and Somaliland. There are 339 schools in Benadir region, which are 30% of all schools assessed, 312 in Hirshabelle (27 %), 178 in South West (15%), 176 in Jubaland (15%) and 154 schools for Galmudug (13%). (MECHE, 2019)

Table 1: Enrolment summary from 2013-2019

School Type	Gender	2012-2013	2013-2014	2014-2015	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019
Primary	Male	44998	42887	N/A	119536	128937	135944	142950
	Female	36328	36020	N/A	94562	104520	110920	117319
	Total	1 81,326	78,907	N/A	214,098	233,457	246,863	260,269
Secondary	Male	11725	14362	N/A	37309	48740	49937	51133
	Female	7323	9688	N/A	25487	36842	36041	35240
	Total	1 19,048	24,050	N/A	62,796	85,582	85978	86373
Total		100374	102957	N/A	276,894	319039	332841	346642

Source: Ministry of Education Culture and Higher Education, Annual Education Statistics Yearbook: 2018/2019

Despite the progress made in education sector, several challenges still face the education sector generally, such as inadequate finance, low capacity of staff at the MoECHE, low and inconsistent salary payments, lack of minimal standards of service and extremely low educational budgets. These challenges continue to impede the effective delivery of

education services in all regions. Communities offer a large part of schooling, which puts an extra burden on parents especially in the rural areas. (MECHE, 2019). The education authorities face substantial resource and capacity restrictions, and have struggled to coordinate inputs at decentralized levels, in particular, stakeholders appear to have limited inputs, in spite of recent progress and achievements in this regard. As such, when considering strategies and approaches to implement the recommendations in this section, partners may wish to consider how to ensure the appropriate consultation and inclusion of stakeholders outside of Mogadishu on decisions, which may affect them. (MECHE, JRES, 2019). Some member states have developed their own policies and strategies to fit into their unique contexts and leverage their diverse potentials. For instance, Somaliland, Puntland and Jubaland state has enacted a local policy. (MECHE, 2019)

Challenges and Opportunities for Curriculum Reforms

Curriculum reform has a dubious reputation, with more sobering than real and lasting success stories. ‘Change in education is easy to propose, hard to implement, and extraordinarily difficult to sustain’. (Cuban, 1992; Fullan, 2007; Leyendecker, 2008). (Hargreaves and Fink (2006).

The Ministry of Education developed a National Curriculum Framework in 2017, the document guides how the curriculum vision is translated into practice at the school level developed (MECHE, JRES, 2019). The lower primary education curriculum has revised, particularly in the early grades; the (grade 1-grade2) textbooks have been distributed to some regions in 2018. The upper primary textbooks were also

developed later, published and planned to distribute in 2019. All curriculum textbooks in low primary, upper primary and secondary are completed in 2020. (MECHE, 2020) Though, schools are implementing the syllabus based on the new curriculum, still the precise number of schools using the textbooks is unknown. However, ensuring sufficient proliferation and training on the new country-wide curriculum and materials could therefore not only help set clear expectations but also allow for effective comparison of schools. A positive aspect of the new curriculum, which was noted by interviewees, was the fact that the new curriculum is written and delivered in Somali language, rather than English language and/or Arabic, which aids understanding on the part of students. (MECHE, JRES, 2019) Importantly, not all learning materials currently used in schools are aligned to the curriculum framework. The challenges are aggravated by the absence of a revised teacher code of conduct. At the same time, divisions of authority between federal and regional governments are remains contested with a lack of clarity over accountabilities for service provision across federal and regional government structures and ongoing debates over decentralized state building, which in turn risk inflaming clan-based conflicts and aggravating inequities in the country. (MECHE, JRES, 2016). There are many visible gaps in the current curriculum such as:

- 1) Although the curriculum reformed, there is a lack of internal consistency within the curriculum design.
- 2) Insufficient cooperation between various actors in educational development.

- 3) Poor capacity of curriculum development department to develop and implement a curriculum capable of delivering quality education in the country.
- 4) The organization of the textbooks and printing is very poor.
- 5) Many teachers are not train on the curriculum.

Teacher's development; Challenges and Opportunities

Before 2012, there has been no data or any real statistics on the teachers sector, which runs the schooling system in the country. The gap vacated by the government since its collapse in 1991 filled by private institutions. However, the ministry recently undertaken some assessment mechanisms to train small number of teachers in Somali National University (SNU) and Mogadishu University and (FPENS). Although ministry of education undertaking some efforts to accelerate arranging school system data management in the country, however there is a big challenge including teacher training infrastructure, policy, teacher code of conduct and lack of a tough teacher management system and a strong accountable supervisory mechanism is the key detriments to the strengthening of the education process.

The Education Sector Strategic Plan (ESSP) indicated that 'The MECHE has tried to improve the teacher training infrastructure situation through auctioning the building of new teacher training facilities. There are two teacher-training institutes that are already operational (one in Hargeisa and another in Garowe).

Table 2: Teachers Summary for the year 2018/19

School Type	Gender	2012-2013	2013-2014	2014-2015	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019
Primary	Male	2126	2219	N/A	5639	5790	6033	6275
	Female	273	399	N/A	505	681	890	1098
Secondary	Male	1171	1205	N/A	2788	3245	3178	3110
	Female	33	57	N/A	57	115	127	139
Total		3603	3880		8989	9831	10227	10622

Source: MECHE, Annual Education Statistics Yearbook: 2018/2019.

The above table shows the number of teachers in the school years of 2012-2013 and 2013-2014, estimation covers Banadir region because the ministry's overall capacity is limited, there is no functioning public schools except few low capacity schools in Banadir region. The initiative of the ministry and UNICEF in Go2School program in 2013 was unsuccessful and totally collapsed. So no qualified teachers were inherited. In 2015-2019 Teachers Summaries covered only ten regions from four federal member states and Benadir apart from Puntland and Somaliland. There was no data assessed by the government in 2014-2015, school year. This is indicated by the vulnerability of the teacher development sector.

The Somali education system dominated by private sector and community education institutions from Quranic schools to higher education levels managed by umbrella organizations. In Banadir region alone has 24 public and 324 private schools according to the MoECHE,

Education Management Information System (EMIS) data for the year 2017.

With so many diverse data about the quality of teachers in the country, it has become necessary to evaluate the status of basic skill and capacity of the teachers. Teacher Proficiency Testing programme (TPT) conducted by the federal ministry of education and its partners in the first time in 2019, determining the teacher competencies in teaching methodology (pedagogy) and subject content skills in the subjects of Mathematics, Somali Language, Islamic Studies as well as English Language. The program implemented in Banadir region teachers only as a pilot. (TPT, Assessment Report, MECHE, 2019).

The (TPT) program provides findings that despite the good teaching and learning environment both primary and secondary school teachers have very little knowledge of how to deliver the subject content. In comparison between the public and private primary schools, the scenario of performance in pedagogy isn't very different. The variation between the trained and untrained teachers' performance in Pedagogy isn't also very significant level. However, there is an indication show that teachers with higher qualifications have relatively better performed in all subjects including pedagogy. In the term of the primary school teachers in both public and private teacher performs is poor in all subjects except Somali Language. The English Language and pedagogy has dismissal performance across all categories of teachers. (TPT, Pilot Assessment Report, MECHE 2019) The ministry of education conducted to recruit the qualified teachers, manage them professionally, remunerate, while

executing a robust code of conduct with consequences for indiscipline not in place (MECHE, 2019).

Examination and Certification; Challenges and Opportunities

Progression in education should be defined in the education policy and curriculum frameworks or qualifications policy to enable education institutions give students' quality testing mechanisms to allow them to compete in the job market. The MoECHE started to organize centralized secondary leaving certificate examination in 2014. Prior of that date this examination was administered by umbrellas of the schools. (MECHE, Examination & Certification Department, 2019) The ministry examination management imparked many challenges including poor ability to plan exams, invigilate and marks. In 2018, the centralized secondary school exam started on Saturday, May 19, 2018. The Ministry announced the test result on July 25, 2018 by a letter from the minister's office. (MECHE, Examination & Certification Department, 2019)

Table 3: Number of the students and their locations (2018)

Location	Number of students	%
Benadir	23161	80%
Galmudug	1306	4.6%
Hirshabelle	1821	7%
Southwest	2340	6%
Jubbland	806	2.4%
Total	25,628	100%

(MECHE, Examination & Certification Department, 2019)

The total number of the boys was 16,520, equivalent to 64%. And the girls total was (9,108), equivalent to 36%. - The number of students who passed in this exam equivalent to 19,537 (78%), while 5,641 (22%) failed. The number of students in this year was higher 32% than the previous 2017; their total reached 18,600 students. (MECHE, Examination & Certification Department, 2019).

In 2019, the secondary school exam took place on May 17, 2019; the total number of the students was 29,434. The ministry announced the result on July 23, 2019, through it's new website: www.soneb.gov.so

Table 4: Number of the students and their locations (2019)

Location	Number of students	%
Benadir	23161	79%
Galmudug	1306	4%
Hirshabelle	1821	6%
Southwest	2340	8%
Jubbland	806	3%
Total	29,434	100%

(MECHE, Examination & Certification Department, 2019)

The number of the boys was (18,584), equivalent to 63%, while the number of girls estimated (10,850) (37%). The number of students passed the exam was equivalent to 76%, while it is 24% fells. - The total number of students in 2019 was more than 15% in 2018. (MECHE, Examination & Certification Department, 2019)

Challenges and Opportunities for Higher Education

Along with the government university, private institutions and businesses are taking keen interest to create many higher education universities. The department of culture & higher education has the responsibility to develop quality assurance mechanism to standardize higher education in the country, but inconsistent ministerial policy at federal and member states level, the department has only embarked on to assess and register the exits universities without accreditation to ensure set up a platform for quality higher education regulation arrangement in the near future.

In the Education Sector Strategic Plan (ESSP) 2018-2020 prepared by the MOECHE, the following challenges have been highlighted in the higher education subsector:

- There are no comprehensive national higher education laws and no national commission for higher education; despite nominated five people as commission without clear policy and strategy.
- The sector is run with no curricula guidance or quality benchmarks or other key forms of support.
- Weaknesses and deficiencies in university management system, including the absence of clear regulations governing such processes, while challenges persist in the governance structure such as poorly defined lines of authority and delegation.

- Fees charged by private universities may be prohibitive and could exclude many eligible Somali students from entering into higher education.

The higher education sector in Somalia requires the legal and policy backing external quality assurance agency. The Education Sector Strategic Plan (ESSP) 2018-2020 stated that “The Ministry of Education, Culture & Higher Education will establish a higher education commission comprised of representative from federal and federal member state levels. The commission will be established with its functions and duties to be agreed upon and officially mandated once the Higher Education Act is officially ratified by parliament”. Unfortunately, the commission established by the minister without specific law provides operational autonomy and separate financing under a ministry, and without proper mandate and consultation with the various education stakeholders. Generally, the main categories of external quality assurance agency are: (Tempus tne-qa, module 4, EN CIS Europe).

- 1) **Governmental**, whereby the agency operates directly under a ministry; for example, (Supreme Council of Universities, Egypt)
- 2) **Quasi-governmental**, the agency is established by a specific law that provides operational autonomy and separate financing under a ministry like (Commission for Higher Education - Kenya; Commission for Higher Education - South Africa).
- 3) **Private independent**, the agency is independent in operation and financing, not under the control of any other stakeholders; (Council for Higher Education Accreditation, United States of America (CHEA-USA); Quality Assurance Agency (QAA-United Kingdom)

- 4) **Professional association**, where member institutions agree on sets of rules, standards and guidelines that would govern them and the processes and procedures to be followed in determining compliance.

The findings of the Education Sector Analysis (2016) indicate, “The current state of university and higher education in Somalia requires firm intervention in order to align practices in the subsector with national policy and improve quality and relevance. The Higher Education Commission has been appointed in July 2019 to put in place the Quality Assurance mechanisms and guidelines for universities and improve the quality standards for universities in Federal Government of Somalia. (MECHE, JRES, 2019). Although, two higher education commissions in Somaliland and Puntland set up in three years ago. The proposed Commission for Higher Education in federal ministry of education now is look like a semi-autonomous/quasi-government agency that would receive some level of funding through government budget provision. It however carries out its functions based on policies and work plans that are approved and regulated by its own governing body (Commissioners). It may also levy fees for services rendered to higher education institutions, individuals and organizations and otherwise raise additional funds to facilitate financing of its entire operation.

The commission needs long time to develop a robust performance framework to review the quality of teaching, scholarships and external engagement of academic staff and engage with institutions to enable them collectively meet the national priorities, without wasteful duplication.

The commission has many challenges to overcome including lack of specific law that provides the commission's mandate to be operationally autonomy and separate financing under the ministry or could be independent in operation and financing, not under the control of any other stakeholders. Higher Education Act still isn't officially ratified by parliament. (MECHE, Education Sector Strategic Plan (ESSP) 2018-2020).

Discussion of Findings

Due to high rates of school abrasion and poor learning outcomes, as well as weak capacities, which effective services deliver, there is a growing need for regulation in all education sectors. The needs come into key factors across the subsectors that could affect learning and enrolment in the schools. In the recently established federal government structures, laws and policies on decentralization of administrative functions for social services have not yet been completed. At the same time accountability and transparency mechanism remains weak in terms of reporting on results and utilization of resources. The proportion of the national budget allocated to the education still is inadequate as the federal and state levels make little budgetary allocation.

Although there was some progress in the education process, still some challenges exist. The federal ministry of education formulated national education policies and guidelines, strategies and standards, curricula and teacher administration system, but that entire document not ratified by the parliament.

There is a strong correlation between lacks a coherent education policy reforms and a system performance to monitor the occurrence and impact of different types of learning. The education system also lacks an agreed upon legal framework to guide decentralizing education services. The challenges affected by poor regulatory environment and coordination between the federal and state level including clear accountabilities between different levels of administration.

The Internal and external capacity has had crucial influences on the ability in the system delivery to provide quality education services to the public.

The study used a documentary study included analyzing existing documents in the ministry and related agencies in the last four years to shed light on the performance and development of the education service delivery, determining the challenges and opportunities in the subsectors developments. The analysis included;

1. Internal and external capacity of the system,
2. Reviewing and determining adequacy of the education system structures, management and responsibilities.
3. Analyzing systems, processes and mechanisms for performing the functions to determine the efficiency.
4. Assessing the human capacity and skill gaps as well as suitability for tasks undertaken.
5. Assessing automation gaps to determine modernization needs.

The external and internal finding is undertaken in line with the PESTEL and SWOT Analysis.

1. A PESTEL analysis is a framework or tool used to analyze and monitor the macro-environmental factors that may have a profound impact on an organization's performance. The letters stand for Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental and Legal.

Table 5: Summary of PESTEL Analysis

Political Factors	Economic Factors	Socio-Culture Factors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal and policy framework still not officially ratified by parliament. • Strong correlation between lacks a coherent education policy reforms and system performances. • Security problems in various parts of the country • Poor data management in the education sectors • Limited control over education services • Weak systems and structures to support federal states coordination. • Lack of clear operational policy framework between staff at federal, state and region levels. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inadequate financial resources • Limited financial capacity to maintain education service in general. • Frequency delays for the school- teachers and administration salaries. • High poverty level in the communities. • Natural crisis such as floods, droughts and diseases. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inequality salary between the civil servant in the government and teachers across the country. • Low payment for teachers and education staff • Weakness of social awareness in their education system partnership.

Technological Factors	Environmental Factors	Legal Factors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of strategy to develop social ability of technology • Poor technology equipment for education development and management. • Limit of necessary technology skills and systems for education staff. • Lack of technical training to develop relevant education materials. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limit of clean environment • Poor of transport facilities • Fear of violence due to insecurity. • Problem of street blockage and checkpoints. • Pandemic of COVID-19 • Poor infrastructure and equipment in the schools • Transportation challenges for students and teachers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal framework weakness totally in • various education sectors, including staff management, service delivery, coordination and supervision.

2. SWOT Analysis

SWOT analysis is a planning technique used to identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats related to education deliver services in Somalia. The strengths and weaknesses determine the positive and negative internal environment while the opportunities and threats assist in assessing the external environment.

Table 6: Summary of SWOT Analysis

Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establishment of the Education Sector Strategic plan 2018-2020 2. Reestablished secondary leaving certificate examination from 2014 - 2020 3. Establishment of interim Higher Education Commission, July 2019 4. Improved education information management technologies. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Regulatory environment for the education sector have not been addressed. 2. Weakness of education administration system 3. Weakness of training facilities among federal and states levels. 4. Weakness of staff capacity and lack of expertise at critical levels. 5. Inadequate infrastructure and equipment. 6. Limit financial resources. 7. Uncoordinated with education partners. 8. Poor education infrastructure in the state level. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increased community participation in the education services delivery. 2. Increased private contributions to support education sector envelopment perfectly. 3. Increase role of diaspora, and their contributions in the private education sector. 4. Increase global partnership and relationship in the education sector. 5. Improved school data collection mechanisms. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increased insecurity in some parts of the country. 2. Limit of partnerships mechanism between ministry of education in federal and state levels to expand access. 3. Unclear data disaggregation between federal and federal member states.

The challenge is more related about the education policies reforms, weakness of the systems and structures to support federal states coordination and staff capacity and inadequate financial resources. However, the insecurity in various parts of the country is major constrain delays establishment and monitoring of sustainable education systems. But to set up reformed draft education policy, education sector strategy plan and coordinate curriculum framework was an opportunity in

education sector policies and strategies in 2016-2020 to promote quality education. Discussion of risks cut across education service delivery and sector related to governance, learning and inequity are addressed by combining into the national development priorities for building a peaceful and prosperous. The government capacities to plan for and mitigate impacts remain weak to non-existent. The main findings of the study including:

1. Poor alignment of strategies and targets across different administrative levels (Region, State and Federal) the key policy documents related to decentralization of social services.
2. Capacity building programs and training for ministry of education personnel, in federal and state level has been entirely dependent upon donors. This has damaged an intelligible government led system strengthening approach, with most beneficiaries of training being drawn from federal level.
3. There are sets of risks facing Somali education system such as conflict related risks and governance risks through different forms of corruption and the perpetuation of social and political inequities.
4. Evidence shows that; management systems related to human resources, recruitment, procurement, as well as weak financial and accountability expose the education system to inefficiencies, political manipulation and corruption.
5. Completion of the national curriculum frameworks has been an important development to ensure greater relevance of education for

learning. However, insufficient resource has meant that the curriculum has yet incompetently and poor purpose.

6. The objective of majority private universities in Somalia is for business regardless of quality education, the sector needs quality regulation, which is use a combination of capacity building, inspections and external evaluations to achieve the desired outcomes of quality and reliable education.
7. No clear line of management coordination between the federal government and members of federal states.
8. The higher education sector data is currently not collected and arranged, this attitude an additional challenge for the ministry of education in evaluating the long-run effects of its policies, transition rates to higher education, and delays in collecting and analyzing data.

Recommendations

With some opportunities on the education system in the last four years, the sector needs to concentrate the challenges and create an environment for quality education in particular:

1. Financial constraints such as expenditure on national education budget and related infrastructure are the key parameter for the government to judge the quality of education.
2. Transparent planning processes for the distribution of available resources in regions and federal states based on education needs based criteria to be developed in partnership with the Ministry of Finance and Ministry of Planning.

3. Strengthen partnerships between Federal and State levels; maintain the decentralized mandate and policy towards provision education in the local communities.
4. Develop a standardized teacher training system covering pre- and in-service training and mentoring linked to quality assurance systems through school supervision based on government quality standards for teaching and learning.
5. Greater research is required on the role of decentralization with improving efficiency of services and access to education.
6. Quality Assurance systems need to be developed and implemented.
7. A substantial effort and investment is required to implement the recently completed national curriculum framework across all schools with corresponding learning materials and textbooks available together with training and resource materials made available for teachers.
8. Capacity development strategies for strengthening government systems should be developed to increase the skills of education personnel to manage education services perfectly.

Reference

- Annual Education Statistics Yearbook: 2018/2019
- Education Sector Strategic Plan (ESSP) 2018-2020
- <http://files.unicef.org/transparency/documents/Somalia%204.%20Education.pdf>
- <http://www.socialwatch.org/node/15979>
- <https://reliefweb.int/report/somalia/somalia-education-cluster-annual-report-2016-january-2017>
- <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/post2015>
- https://www.tne-qa.com/images/public/04_EQA_Tempus_MODULE_4_EN_CIS_Europe.
- MECHE, Teacher Proficiency Testing Pilot Assessment Report for Banadir Region, September, 2019
- Ministry of Education (2019). Global Partnership for Education: Report on School Mapping and needs assessment of FGS/FMS schools.
- Ministry of Education Culture and Higher Education (MECHE), (2011) Interim Education Sector Strategic Plan (2013 - 2016).
- Ministry of Education Culture and Higher Education (MECHE), (2017) The Somalia Education Act.
- Ministry of Education Culture and Higher Education, Annual Joint Reviews of the Education Sector (JRES) Aug 2019
- Ministry of Education Culture and Higher Education, Annual Joint Reviews of the Education Sector (JRES) 2018
- Ministry of Education Culture and Higher Education, the national development plan 2017-2019
- Ministry of planning, Population Estimate Survey for Somalia (PESS, 2014)

Re-Organization and Modernization of Ministry of Education Culture and Higher Education, Patrick Kimathi, consulting report, 2019

Sadegh Bakhtiari, Globalization and Education Challenges and Opportunities. International Business & Economic Research Journal, Vol 5, 2011

TVET Market Analysis, Skills for youth in Mogadishu, Concern Worldwide, 2016 Forcier Consulting

UNESCO. (2011). UNESCO Global Fund Monitoring Report. Mogadishu: UNESCO.

UNICEF, Education Sector Analysis (2016)